

IgA-AS A MARKER FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF NEPHROPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH REACTIVE ARTHRITIS

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Relevance. Kidney injury during RA includes secondary renal amyloidosis, nephrotoxic effects of antirheumatic drugs and nephropathies as extra-articular manifestations (rheumatoid nephropathy). Amyloidosis affects survival, increases morbidity and is the main cause of end stage renal disease in patients with RA and nephropathy [1,4,9]. Amyloidosis is a group of diseases characterized by extracellular deposition of beta-sheet fibrils. In the systemic forms, the amyloid protein causes progressive organ dysfunction, which may lead to death of the patients [2,5,10]. Over 35 proteins capable of amyloid formation have been identified. Clinically evident kidney involvement most commonly occurs in AL (immunoglobulin light chain) or AA (previously referred to as secondary) amyloidosis but can also occur in other forms of amyloidosis [3,6,7,8]. The deposition of beta-2 microglobulin occurs in patients on prolonged maintenance dialysis; deposition in the kidney has been reported in autopsies but has no clinical significance. IgA nephropathy (IgAN) may be associated with reactive arthritis (RA). The course of RA-associated IgAN remains largely unknown due to the absence of large numbers of patients.

Purpose of the study. To determine the role of IgA as a marker for the diagnosis of nephropathy in patients with reactive arthritis.

Materials and research methods. This retrospective study included patients with biopsy-proven IgAN and definite RA. Kidney biopsies were examined centrally and evaluated according to the Oxford classification of IgAN. Thirty-two patients met the inclusion criteria, with a male to female ratio of 9:1 and a mean age of 27

and 37 years at the time of diagnosis of RA, respectively. HLA-B27 was positive in 90% of cases and the majority of patients (60%) had RA. The mean estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) at baseline was 84 ± 26 ml/min per 1.73 m², and the urinary protein to creatinine ratio was 0.19 g/mmol.

Results. Renal biopsy revealed frequent crescents (33%) and interstitial inflammation (18%). Despite almost constant use of renin-angiotensin system inhibitors in combination with steroids in 13 of 32 patients, the renal outcome was particularly poor. After a median follow-up of 5.9 years, 4 patients (12.5%) developed end-stage renal disease, and 41% of patients had a decrease in eGFR >50%. The mean annual eGFR decline rate was -4.3 ± 6.7 ml/min per 1.73 m² and Oxford T-scores.

Conclusion. RA-associated IgAN is associated with poor renal outcome despite frequent steroid use. Blockade of tumor necrosis factor (TNF)- α did not seem to affect the rate of decline in eGFR under these conditions.

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